

FACTORS OF STEP-BY-STEP FORMATION OF PSYCHOLOGICAL QUALITIES IN MANAGEMENT SPECIALISTS

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ABSTRACT

This article covers the general definition of the word management, the field of management, its subject and tasks. In addition, there are necessary points about the stages of formation of psychological qualities in a management specialist, as well as their essence and foundations. The article was analyzed analytically. The article mentions the processes and features of the management field as one of the principles of the market.

Management (English: management) management, organization) special management activity; management science. Management is handled by qualified specialists who have received special training and are well versed in the rules of management - hired managers - managers. They form a separate social stratum of the population. There are upper (developing the company's strategy), middle (production, sales, pricing, labor organization), and lower (organization of work within the workshop, department, managing the execution of daily, weekly, monthly tasks) links of management. Accordingly, managers are divided into senior, middle and junior managers.

It is not difficult to imagine that thousands of enterprises based on different ownership operate in the market economy. Organization of the management of enterprises at one or another level depends on the management ability of the head of the enterprise. His ability is measured by the extent to which he has acquired knowledge in the field of management. From this point of view, the word "management" has become one of the words associated with the market economy in our lives. Management (English management) means organization and management of one or another type of activity, organization and management of economic, financial and other business spheres of human life. It is the type of management necessary for a market economy and a free link of a production economy.

Although the English word "management" means management, originally it meant to bring down horses. Later, this term began to be used for a two-wheeled cart. Today, it is about managing people and teams. In this place, it is understood to achieve the goals by using people's work and will.

Thus, the term "management" means the following:

1. Management;
2. The field of knowledge in the human body;

3. The social stratum of those who implemented management

The principles of management psychology are the basic ideas, psychological patterns and rules of behavior of managers for the implementation of management functions.

The main principles of management psychology are:

1. Management is an integral part of human existence. Without management, the joint activity of people is absolutely impossible. Management allows effective implementation of strong psychological qualities of people, eliminating weak ones.

2. Under the influence of cultural and historical traditions, management has deeply entered the psychology of leaders of all countries, and they basically perform the same tasks and functions.

3. Any organization needs simple and clear goals that unite all employees. In this regard, the task of management psychology is to establish a system of values and motives that can make all employees partners in the team.

4. The task of management psychology is to give the team and each of its members the opportunity to develop their abilities, improve their personal qualities, and fully satisfy their needs.

5. Each employee should be based on personal discipline and responsibility in the process of work; he should be able to clearly express his duties and evaluate his personal contribution to the overall work.

One of the first requirements for the qualities of a leader is his ability to create a team. How the team is organized by one or more leaders depends on the success of its management. In this regard, certain psychological requirements are placed on the leader. A leader must have a creative but realistic vision. It is important for the manager to be able to see in each employee the structure of qualities that should be a candidate for the position, to correctly select and place employees.

Team building is related to solving the problem of psychological compatibility. This requires the leader to know the psychological characteristics of employees and how to take them into account when forming special directions of the team. This approach allows him to influence the formation of the best social-psychological environment in the team.

American and Japanese studies in the field of sustainable performance management show that firms with a peaceful moral and psychological environment can achieve.

Laws of mutual understanding. If the employees you lead do not understand what is required of them, they will not be able to fulfill the assigned task. The leader must be able to convey the task to the subordinates in an understandable way. For some employees, one word is enough, and for some, a long explanation is necessary. The leader should get along with his employees in such a way that they not only listen to you, but also hear you.

Understanding - using the hearing organs, hearing - attracting one's attention, using the brain. Brain training is essential for effective completion of a given task. The following 5 conditions are considered to be the main factors in employees' understanding of their superiors:

- unity of profession;
- taking into account the level of intelligence;
- completeness of information;

- the logic of the statement;
- concentration of attention.

Understanding depends on the speaker's tone of voice. It is difficult to understand such a leader if, while giving assignments, it is always emphasized that subordinates do not understand, if they speak in a rude tone. In this case, the attention of the listening person is focused not on the content of the task, but on the behavior and behavior of the person speaking. In any situation, people are quick to communicate with people they like, on the contrary, it is difficult for them to agree on the point of view of people they do not like. This "law" originates from a person's own life, from the characteristics of his psychology. For a person, spiritual climate is more important than physical climate. There will be more talk about how to manage this factor, how to involve it in leadership services, how to use it in leadership communication, and how to guide it. Psychological ways of making the subordinates inclined to him. Ways to attract employees are called attraction. When we talk to a person, our sense organs (sight, hearing, smell, etc.) receive many messages from him. But people cannot accept all these messages consciously. For example, after an active conversation, if you are asked to close your eyes for a minute and tell the color of your interlocutor's tie, you will not always be able to answer correctly. So, we can see and not see, listen and hear, it depends on how our mind works. At the same time, messages of emotional significance are preserved in a person. "name-name" method. This method starts with saying the name of the person you are talking to. It is always pleasant for a person to hear his name in full from others. As the American psychologist D. Carnegie wrote, hearing one's name from others is like pleasant music for a person.

What are the psychological mechanisms of this condition? The psychological mechanisms of this method are as follows:

1. The name given to a person is always next to him. The name cannot be divided by the person.
2. If a person is addressed without mentioning his name, this means that he is being addressed only for service purposes. If you address a person by name, it means that you are paying attention to him.
3. Calling by name is recognition of a person as a person.
4. When a person feels that he is a person, he will definitely feel satisfied.
5. The feeling of satisfaction always depends on positive emotions.
6. A person always tries to please someone, wants someone to treat him well.
7. If someone makes us feel positive, he attracts us, and we want to communicate closely with him.

Socio-psychological method of management is the practical implementation of the necessary conscious, active, continuous labor activity of organizational teams, which is carried out on the basis of mutual mental stimulation of people. The development of socio-psychological methods of management is based on the application of the existing social mechanism (system of interaction, social needs). Social methods of management are implemented through social regulation. Methods of social regulation are used to regulate and harmonize social relations by identifying and aligning the goals and interests of different groups and individuals. They include regulations of social organizations, contracts, mutual obligations, labor selection, distribution and system of meeting social needs. Methods of social

regulation are also used in order to increase the activity of the human factor and democratize management. Socio-psychological methods of management are aimed at regulating relations between people by creating an acceptable psychological state in the team. Psychological methods include organizing small groups and teams, selecting qualified personnel, training them, etc. The socio-psychological method affects each team and its employee. They include: methods of persuasion, training, moral stimulation, meeting the domestic demands of employees, and maintaining and developing the team's advanced labor traditions.

The word control is used in a broad sense, for example: control of a state, control of a machine, control of any biological process, etc.

The word management is mainly used in the management of socio-economic processes in market conditions at the firm level. Management unites workers with various independence, namely engineers, designers, economists, statisticians, psychologists, accountants. All these are managed by the manager. The management process, first of all, begins with the determination of its highest goal and, at the same time, with the development of a program of actions necessary for its implementation. It is known that planning is one of the main functions of management. Planning, first of all, is defining the future, choosing promising directions for increasing efficiency. It consists in developing the most optimal options for decisions and ensuring their implementation. An important area of planning today is predicting the future. Forecasting the future is done through mathematical modeling using economic mathematical methods. Economic methods of management are a small part of the full economic mechanism, and with their help, the problem of production efficiency is solved. These methods affect the management through the creation of a certain situation based on the system of economic indicators, economic and material incentives, and economic levers such as price and credit.

The most important point in the management process is management decision making. Every leader should be able to see the problems related to the conditions of the system he manages. Every leader must develop a new sense, the ability to analyze, to distinguish the most important questions from countless information and facts. Systematization of one's experience and ideas ready for their use, when necessary, is an important condition for organizing the scientific work of the leader. Another quality that characterizes a good leader when studying a particular decision is the sense of responsibility that should be attached to the decision. The ability to advise the manager to identify and choose the most appropriate approach to solving the problem is of great importance. The manager's ability to give advice significantly determines the effectiveness of his work. The ability to analyze people's thoughts is very important for a leader.

If the leader not only explains his way to his subordinates, but wants to get them to agree with him and feel his point of view, he needs to constantly enrich his knowledge about human psychology.

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